

SHORT COMMUNICATIONS

New Syntheses of Isomeric Methyl Carbazoles

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Our interest on naturally occurring carbazole derivatives^{1,2} prompted the syntheses of isomeric methyl carbazoles. 1- and 3-methyl carbazoles have been synthesised using Borsche method by various workers. Borsche method^{3,4} does not provide for unambiguous syntheses of 2- and 4-methyl carbazoles. 2- and 4-Methyl carbazoles free from each other have been synthesised by Szmuszkowicz⁵ and by Pausacker and Robinson⁶ respectively. 2-Methyl carbazole was obtained as a bye product (10% yield) during the reaction of 2-methyl indole with MVK, while a compound C₁₃H₁₅NO, m.p. 199-201° was obtained as a bye product during the synthesis of 4-methyl carbazole.

- (A) 1-Methyl carbazole and its precursors; R₁ = -CH₃, R₂=R₃=R₄=H
 (B) 2-Methyl carbazole and its precursors; R₂ = -CH₃, R₁=R₃=R₄=H
 (C) 3-Methyl carbazole and its precursors; R₃ = -CH₃, R₁=R₂=R₄=H
 (D) 4-Methyl carbazole and its precursors; R₄ = -CH₃, R₁=R₂=R₃=H

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We now report a general method for the synthesis of all the isomeric methyl carbazoles using Japp-Klingemann reaction and subsequent indolisation by Fischer process as followed in the synthesis of glycozoline⁷. The reaction intermediates are readily separable and the final products are obtained in good yield. Appropriate hydroxymethylene cyclohexanone or its derivatives (I) on condensation with phenyldiazonium chloride or its derivatives (II) furnished the hydrazone (III) which was cyclised to tetrahydro-oxo-carbazole (IV) using a mixture of acetic acid and concentrated hydrochloric acid as the cyclising agent. The tetrahydro/carbazoles (V) obtained by Wolff-Kishner-Huang-Minlon reduction of the oxo-compound (IV) furnished on dehydrogenation with Pd/C in p-cymene the desired carbazole derivatives (VI). The reactions are shown above and physical properties of all the different intermediates and final products are shown in Table I. The methyl carbazoles were found homogeneous by paper chromatography⁸ and their uv. spectra were in conformity with those of isomeric methyl carbazoles⁹. 1-, 2-, 3-Methyl carbazoles were identified by mixed melting point determination with the samples prepared in the conventional way¹⁰.

TABLE I*

Hydroxymethylene Starting cyclohexanone	amines	Properties of hydrazone	Properties of oxo-tetrahydrocarbazole	Properties of tetrahydrocarbazole	Properties of carbazole
2-Hydroxymethylene cyclohexanone	O-toluidine	III(A) red flexy crystals, $C_{13}H_{16}N_2O$, m.p. 94-5°	IV(A) white needles, $C_{13}H_{13}NO$, m.p. 165-6°	V(A) unstable solid mass, m.p. 96-7° (lit. m.p. 97-98°)	VI(A) white crystals $C_{13}H_{11}N$, m.p. 118-9° (lit. m.p. 120.5°)
2-hydroxymethylene-6-methyl cyclohexanone	Aniline	III(B) red coloured liquid	IV(B) white needles, $C_{13}H_{13}NO$, m.p. 164-5°	V(B) crystalline solid, $C_{13}H_{15}N$, m.p. 96-8° (lit. m.p. 98-9°)	VI(B) white crystals, $C_{13}H_{11}N$, m.p. 260-2° (lit. m.p. 260°)
2-hydroxymethylene cyclohexanone	p-toluidine	III(C) Brown flexy crystals, $C_{13}H_{16}N_2O$, m.p. 131-2°	IV(C) white crystals, $C_{13}H_{13}NO$, m.p. 131-2°	V(C) white crystals, $C_{13}H_{15}N$, m.p. 148-50° (lit. m.p. 141-2°)	VI(C) white crystals, $C_{13}H_{11}N$, m.p. 206-7° (lit. m.p. 207°)
2-hydroxymethylene -4-methyl cyclohexanone	Aniline	III(D) light brown crystals, $C_{13}H_{16}N_2O$, m.p. 137-40°	IV(D) white crystals, $C_{13}H_{13}NO$, m.p. 145-6°	V(D) very unstable solid turns to coloured oil	VI(D) white crystals, $C_{13}H_{11}N$, m.p. 128-30° (lit. m.p. 115-6°)

*All the hydrazones, oxo-tetrahydro carbazoles, tetrahydro carbazoles and carbazoles were purified by column chromatography using alumina as adsorbent. The hydrazones were crystallised from aqueous alcohol and the rest of the compounds were crystallised from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°). Satisfactory analyses were obtained for all the compounds reported with mol. formulae.

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